

Figure S1: Characterization of conditional, forebrain-specific Stau2 knockdown rat (related to Figure 1).

(A) Immunostaining anti-Stau2 (Cy5; red) of primary hippocampal neurons, transiently transfected with a vector co-expressing EGFP (green) and miR(Stau2). Arrowhead indicates a transfected EGFP positive neurons that show almost no signal for Stau2. (B-C) Immunohistochemical analysis for EGFP in forebrain (B) and cerebral cortex (C) of double transgenic CaMKII α -CreERT2 x CAG-STOP-miR(Stau2) rats following vehicle (-Tx) or tamoxifen (+Tx; Stau2^{KD}) injection. (D-F) Quantification by qRT-PCR of *EGFP* (n=4 animals/group) (D), *Stau2* (n=5 animals/group) (E) and *Stau1* (n=5 animals/group) (F) mRNA expression in hippocampal areas of Stau2^{KD} animals (black bars), and compared to CaMKII α -CreERT2 animals (gray bars) (E: $F_{genotype} (1,24) = 172.18$; $p < 0.001$). (G) Quantification of Stau2 protein levels relative to control (as in Figure 1D) in Stau2^{KD} (n=3 animals/group). (H) Dual immunofluorescence visualization of EGFP (Cy2; green) and Stau2 (Cy5; red) within the cerebral cortex; arrowheads indicate Stau2-positive immunostaining in EGFP-negative neurons. (I-J) Analysis of the intron-containing *Calm3* mRNA isoform in control and Stau2 silenced animals: representative images of *in situ* hybridization with *Calm3* intron antisense probe in free-floating adult coronal vibratome sections, showing cortex (left panels) and hippocampus (middle panels, yellow boxes are magnified on the right panels) (I) and qRT-PCR of total *Calm3* mRNA and *Calm3* containing intron in cortical lysates. Bars show mean and SD values from n=3-4 animals/group (J). (K-P) Effect of Stau2 deficiency on dendritic morphology *in vivo*. (K) Representative Golgi-Cox staining of a CA1 dendrite from Tx-injected CaMKII α -CreERT2 (left) and Stau2^{KD} (right) rats. Quantification of dendritic spine density (L,O) and frequency distribution of dendritic spine length in apical (M,P) and basal (N) dendrites of CA1 (L-N) or CA3 (O,P) pyramidal neurons in Stau2^{KD} rats compared to CaMKII α -CreERT2 rats (CA1: $F_{genotype*genotype} (4,32) = 6.32$; $p = 0.0007$) (n=4-5 animals/group). Figures show mean + SEM. Scale bars: 20 μ m (A), 100 μ m (H), 10 μ m (K). Stars represent p-values between genotypes obtained by t-tests (E,L) or Bonferroni post-hoc analysis following two-way ANOVA of repeated measures (M); * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$.

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Figure S2: Stau2 deficiency leads to a shift in the frequency-response function of hippocampal synaptic plasticity favoring synaptic strengthening (related to Figure 2).

(A-B) Input-output relationship is shown as the ratio between the stimuli intensity and the evoked fEPSP slope in the CA1 (A) and CA3 (B) regions of Tx-injected CAG-STOP-miR(Stau2) (dotted line), CaMKII α -CreERT2 (dashed line) or Stau2^{KD} (solid line) rats. (C-D) Paired pulse (PP) facilitation evoked by the second pulse at different stimulus intervals in the CA1 (C) and CA3 (D) regions of Tx-injected CAG-STOP-miR(Stau2) (white), CaMKII α -CreERT2 (gray) or Stau2^{KD} rats (black). (E-H) Representative fEPSPs (E+G, top) and averaged potentiated responses (E+G, bottom) following high frequency stimulation (HFS, E) or low frequency stimulation (LFS, G) of the perforant path (PP) in Tx-injected CAG-STOP-miR(Stau2) (white), CaMKII α -CreERT2 (gray) or Stau2^{KD} rats (black) recorded in CA3. Displayed fEPSPs were taken at time points B, 1 and 2 indicated in the figure. Quantitative analysis of fEPSPs following HFS (F) or LFS (H) in Tx-injected CaMKII α -CreERT2, CAG-STOP-miR(Stau2) and Stau2^{KD} rats (H). Figures show mean + SEM. Statistical significant differences *within groups* are indicated using horizontal bars with circles, *between groups* with stars after two-way ANOVA of repeated measures and all Pairwise Multiple Comparison procedures (Holm-Sidak method), (n=10 animals/group). *, \circ p<0.05.

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Figure S3: Consequences of Stau2 knockdown on hippocampal-dependent spatial learning and memory (related to **Figure 3**).

(**A-D**) Open field test: total distance moved (**A**), percentage of activity (**B**), average speed (**C**) and number of rearings (**D**) during the entire test (30 min) for Tx-injected Stau2^{KD} (black; n=12) and CaMKII α -CreERT2 (gray; n=9) rats. (**E**) Novel object recognition (NOR) task is schematically represented (top), and the preference for the novel object (>50%) is indicated for Tx-injected Stau2^{KD} (black; n=12) and CaMKII α -CreERT2 (gray; n=8) rats. (**F-G**) Hidden platform Morris water maze task: averaged escape latencies over trials during training (**F**) and percentage of time spent in the different quadrants of the water maze during the probe trial on day 4 (**G**) for Tx-injected Stau2^{KD} (black; n=13) and CaMKII α -CreERT2 (gray; n=7) rats. TQ: target quadrant where the platform was located; OQ: the opposite quadrant; AQ: the average of the two adjacent quadrants. (**H**) Plot indicating the latency to enter the arm with the anticipated reward ($F_{genotype*delay\ time}(3,36) = 3.64$; $p = 0.022$) during the choice phase of the delayed non-matching to place (DNMP) task after short (1 min) and intermediate (5 min, 10 min) time delays for Tx-injected CaMKII α -CreERT2 (n=6) and Stau2^{KD} animals (n=8). Figures show mean + or \pm SEM. Hashtags represent p-values of one-sample t-tests to chance level 50%: # $p < 0.05$; ## $p < 0.01$.

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Figure S4: Consequences of Stau2 knockdown on fear learning, memory and operant conditioning (related to **Figure 4**).

(A-C) Delay Fear Conditioning. Schematic representation of the training test is indicated (A; top). Acquisition of conditioned fear shown as time spent freezing plotted over tone-shock pairings (A; bottom), recall of contextual fear displayed as freezing response toward the context in which fear conditioning took place (B) and test for recall of cued fear, in which the freezing response was recorded in a novel context before (pre-cue) and during tone presentation (cue) (C) in Tx-injected CaMKII α -CreERT2 (n=8) and Stau2^{KD} animals (n=13). (D) Extinction of conditioned fear: time spent freezing plotted over tone presentations in the conditioning context for both Tx-injected Stau2^{KD} (black; n=12) and CaMKII α -CreERT2 (gray; n=8) rats. (E,F) Inhibitory avoidance task: on the training day, animals were placed on a platform located in conditioning chamber A (E). Once they stepped down with all 4 paws, rats received a shock and were subsequently removed from context A. 24 h later, animals were tested for their fear memory first in context A (E) and 3 h later in testing context B (F). (G) Schematic representation of the box used for the operant conditioning paradigm. (H) Illustration of the operating conditioning paradigm in the dark, applied to train the animals with a fixed ratio 1 (FR1) protocol. (I) Lever presses during operant conditioning session following the FR1 protocol for Tx-injected CaMKII α -CreERT2 controls and Stau2^{KD} rats. (J) Mean number of lever presses during light and dark periods of rats of both genotypes collected on training day 6 (as shown in **Figure 4E,F**) (n=10 animals/group). (K) Schematic representation of the dual signal recognition task, where the lever (and reward) was removed in 50% of the illuminated periods.